

INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS HAVING H-BOND RING STRUCTURE
AND COMPLEX FORMATION. PART II. THE SYSTEMS
 $\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ AND $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 - \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$

By MISS HEMIATA J. KAZI AND C. M. DESAI

Measurements of interfacial tension between *n*-butyl acetate and *sec.*-octyl alcohol against mixed solutions of KNO_3 (or NH_4NO_3) and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ indicate the formation of three complexes in the systems $\text{KNO}_3 - \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 - \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively.

The complex formation between $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and KNO_3 in solution has been indicated from the study of solubility and cryoscopic measurements (Le Blanc and Noyes, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, 6, 386; Kanitz, *ibid.*, 1897, 22, 347). Glasstone and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2134; 1925, 2846) also added evidence of complex formation and indicated the probable existence of a double salt, viz. $2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. The existence of the complex $2\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was indicated by Malquori (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1928, II, 517; *Atti R. Acad. Lincei*, 1929, 9, 231; *Gazzetta*, 1929, 59, 355) from the study of conductivity and viscosity data of solutions of lead and ammonium nitrates. Recently, Nayar and Pande (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 285, 353; 1949, 30A, 251; this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 112) showed by the study of viscosity, surface tension, E.M.F., transport number, magnetic susceptibility and thermometric titration measurements of mixtures of aqueous solutions of the above nitrates, the formation of complexes:

Narasimha Murthy and others confirmed these findings in the systems by the study of other different properties (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1950, 31A, 160; *Curr. Sci.*, 1950, 19, 240; 1951, 20, 13).

The interfacial tension measurements of *n*-butyl acetate against mixed aqueous solutions of mercuric chloride and potassium chloride (this *issue*, Part I, p. 287) have indicated the formation of seven complexes in solution. The present investigation deals with the study of the systems (a) and (b) studied by Nayar and others (*loc. cit.*) by the authors' method. For the procedure, *n*-butyl acetate was selected for the system (a), and *sec.*-octyl alcohol for (b) to see whether it behaved in an analogous manner to *n*-butyl acetate, as it also seems to have an unstable H-bond ring structure (cf. Miss Kazi and Desai, *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 218).

EXPERIMENTAL

The method of procedure adopted in preparing solutions of the nitrates was that of Nayar and Pande (*loc. cit.*); KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, pure quality (E. Merck), were further purified by repeated crystallisations from distilled water. *sec.*-Octyl alcohol (Schering-Kahlbaum) was distilled and the middle fraction was utilised for interfacial tension measurements.

Either KNO_3 or NH_4NO_3 solutions (20 c.c.) were pipetted into a flask, different volumes of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution were added and the mixture was made up to 60 c.c. with distilled water.

The interfacial tensions were measured by the method described earlier. The results obtained at 30° are shown graphically in Fig. 1.

DISCUSSION

The figure shows peaks corresponding to the formation of the following complexes :

- (a) $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $4\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
 (b) $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $2\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $4\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

FIG. 1

$M/10\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added in c.c. to $M\text{-}10\text{-alkalinitrate}$ (20 c.c.).

These results confirm the findings of Nayar and others (*loc. cit.*). Further, *sec*-octyl alcohol behaves as sensitively as *n*-butyl acetate in the indication of complex formation in solution.

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INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS HAVING H-BOND RING
STRUCTURE AND COMPLEX FORMATION. PART III. THE
SYSTEM $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$

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Measurements of interfacial tension between *n*-butyl acetate against a series of mixed solutions of NaNO_3 and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ indicate the formation of the complexes: (1) $4\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (2) $2\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (3) $\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in solution.